

ISSUES OF SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL RESEARCH OF THE FACTOR OF MUSICAL HERITAGE IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CONTINUOUS SPIRITUAL EDUCATION IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the socio-philosophical research of the musical heritage factor in the implementation of continuous spiritual education in New Uzbekistan, the possibilities of using examples of musical heritage to increase the effectiveness of the continuous spiritual education system, the future tasks of the musical heritage factor in the process of continuous spiritual education studied. The socio-philosophical and conceptual aspects of the continuous spiritual education system are also analyzed.

Key words: continuous spiritual education, musical heritage, socio-philosophical factor, education, dynamics, harmonization, social state, systemic-functional analysis, theoretical-methodological basis, development, social value, cultural context.

INTRODUCTION. Spirituality is a mirror that reveals the inner world of a person. It is the concept of a person's way of living and general life based on certain moral standards. Spirituality is a multifaceted phenomenon and is an integral unity of moral (decency, duty, sense of responsibility), scientific, creative, practical skills (work, creativity, ability), religious and ideological views. The future of spirituality begins in kindergarten. To provide quality education to children in kindergartens, first of all, it is necessary to educate them spiritually. A child who is polite, orderly, and respects the opinions of others also learns well. Therefore, in order to ensure the integrity of spiritual education, the work of providing spiritual education to children in preschool educational institutions has become another important task of educators.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Wide use of examples of musical heritage in the implementation of continuous spiritual education in society and through this, scientific researches on the development of axiological attitude of young people to the national musical heritage, reform of the pedagogical process on the national musical heritage and its preservation, scientific research on determining the axiological attitude to the national musical heritage practical

tasks D. Karomatli, T. Levin, Y. Elsnar, E. Abdulin, YE. Bodina, O. Bochkareva, E. Burzina, N. Ivanov, L. Koval, V. Rajnikov, A. Rapatskaya, S. Bulatov, Researched by scientists such as B. Azimov, S. Annamuratova, O. Vasilchenko, Sh. Janaydarov, F. Joraev, D. Kamolova, H. Nurmatov, F. Khalilov, A. Hasanov. Also, the history, theory, characteristics of Uzbek classical musical heritage, folklore songs, R. Abdullaev, S. Begmatov, T. Vizgo, O. Ibrohimov, F. Karomatov, I. Rajabov, T. Gafurbekov, B. Kadirov, Covered in the works of M. Kadirov, E. Fayzullaev.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Spirituality is an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification, spiritual growth, strengthens his inner world, strengthens his will, completes his faith, awakens his conscience, and is the criterion of all his views. So, it follows that the spirituality of people is different. However, "People cannot be divided into 'spiritual' and non-spiritual ones. Because the human being is born, it is definitely formed as "spiritual" in the process of social development. There is no person without spirituality. Only the spiritual can be good or bad, rich or poor, high or low. The level of spirituality of each person depends on the environment or society that surrounds them. In other words, the spiritual level of a person is determined to a certain extent by the spiritual life of the society in which he lives. Of course, society is a very broad concept, it includes the whole country. However, there are several other spiritual environments or spiritual connections between a person and society, and they also have a special place in the spiritual development of people. These include, first of all, family, neighborhood, school, academic lyceum and colleges, higher educational institutions, various organizations, enterprises, offices. The number of such structural societies is very large, and the level of spiritual environment in them is also diverse. Therefore, our assessment of the spirituality of the society is given in a relatively general way. In any highly spiritual society, there can be "communities" and people with poor or inferior spirituality, even if it is a small amount. Also, on the contrary, there may be highly spiritual people in a spiritually poor society. From this point of view, it can be concluded that in order to raise spirituality, it is necessary to act not in a narrow circle, but on a wide scale.

We must keep in mind that before raising the spirituality of our people, we must first explain to our people what spirituality is, its essence, and purpose. The concept of spirituality, which originally comes from an Arabic word and means a set of meanings, can be given not one, but several definitions. This is

natural. When he says why, he really means a complex of meanings. That is, a combination of several meanings is embodied in the concept of spirituality.

It is important to study the manifestation of the nature of a person who serves for the development of social life as a creator of all material means and social relations as spiritual means. In this process, social relations and forms, the role of spirituality in self-development in a person's social life is considered important. Spirituality creates a certain approach to all spheres of the life of the whole society. That is, spirituality both forms a person and shows his human essence. This describes the measure of mastering different methods of human activity and the development of a person as a self-creating subject of activity, a subject of socio-historical creativity. In our opinion, this is a social mechanism in society, which expresses the content that all its links should be directed to the individual and his development. "The universe is built on the basis of the struggle of opposites: light and darkness in physical things, life in living nature is expressed in the struggle between just laws and injustice." As a result, the concept of spirituality characterizes the social essence of an individual and occupies the main place in the set of social relations attached to them. The methods of forming strategic technologies of personal spirituality include the following elements:

First, increase the ability to perform social activities;

Secondly, knowledge, skills and abilities;

Thirdly, human feelings, i.e., the spiritual influence of a person, are manifested in the forms of culture.

The result of scientific research indicates that the rise of spiritual education in the relationship between the society and the individual means that the individual is based on spirituality in the social process.

Given that there is no single general definition of spirituality, the analysis of philosophical, theological, psychological and pedagogical literature allows us to distinguish the main approach:

First of all, spirituality is considered as the universal spiritual beginning of the world. At the same time, the essence of a person, the potential possibilities of his soul are considered as a measure of acquaintance with this beginning.

Secondly, it shows the internal spiritual absolutes and moral values of a person as representatives of the axiological direction as the principles of harmonization.

Third, proponents of the cognitive approach seek to identify the rational side of mental life. A number of modern authors refer to the sociological aspects

of the study of spirituality and evaluate it as a characteristic of the inner world of a person connected with epistemological and social needs.

Analysis of the essence of spirituality in the accepted research system allows us to say that spirituality is the freedom of self-development of a person as a social essence. Based on this, the activity of adapting to social relations in the form of spiritual knowledge, skills and images of a person is understood.

The methods of formation of strategic technologies of continuous spirituality of the person are aimed at changing the diversity and activity based on the values of the person. The basis of a person's spirituality is the value orientations, which are specific methods that ensure the stability of the person.

Methods of formation of new strategic technologies in continuous spiritual education are the main value of a person's spiritual culture. is able to protect from feelings. Spirituality of a person Changes in society are often the result of changes in the spiritual culture of a person, which are manifested in all social institutions. At the same time, the type of society has a great influence on the development of a person's spiritual culture.

Technologies of spiritual education require the basis of advanced innovative technologies of the field of education. Development occurs as a result of the existence of stable relations between the subjects of socio-cultural technologies in society. The genesis of new strategic technologies in spiritual education appears with the beginning of conclusions and relations as a result of spiritual and educational propaganda.

CONCLUSION. Today, education occupies a special place among social institutions that influence the development of a person's continuous spiritual culture. Therefore, its modernization is of great importance, we can see it as a process of action aimed at cultural, social and personality-oriented education, which ensures the creation of a conscious and responsible life of an individual in a complex changing world. In this place, a new, systematic approach to education, family, pre-school education, general education, secondary special vocational and higher educational institutions, social-pedagogical possibilities of neighborhoods in guaranteeing the formation of basic qualities in a child will be fully realized. issue that requires raising the scientific-methodical coherence between them to a new level is of urgent importance. The need of the society for the idea of national progress and the implementation of spiritual-educational reforms is demanded to rely on new technologies to increase the efficiency of all spheres at the stage of the development of the state and society.

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